

Employing Research Community Networks to Assess Research Software Engineer (RSE) Impact

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Abstract—Collaboration networks for university research communities can be readily rendered through the interrogation of coauthorships and coinvestigator data. Subsequent computation of network metrics such as degree or various centralities offer interpretations on collaborativeness and interdisciplinary activity. Composed into cohort distributions, these metrics can be statistically contrasted. In prior work, this workflow provided quantitative evidence for ROI of centralized computing resources in contrasting researchers with and without cluster accounts, where significance was found across all metrics. In this work, two similar cohorts, those with Research Software Engineer (RSE)-type roles at the university and everyone else, are examined in a similar vein. While a significantly higher degree statistic for the RSE cohort suggests its collaborative value, a significantly lower betweenness centrality distribution indicates a target for potential impact through the implementation of a centralized RSE network.

Index Terms—network metrics, software engineering

I. INTRODUCTION

The workflow presented in this manuscript was previously employed to compare researchers who had used the Arizona State University (ASU) Research Computing Agave compute cluster, represented as one cohort of nodes in the constructed network, to researchers who did not have an account on Agave [1]. In this work, a different cohort composed of Research Software Engineer (RSE) nodes is identified for a similar statistical contrast.

II. NETWORK CONSTRUCTION

A. Dataset

Publication and grant data were collected through the Dimensions API, by specifying ASU researchers and limiting the time span to the years 2012-2022 [2]. Following the general process defined by the KMAP effort, 14 606 total researchers at ASU and 587 external universities were defined as nodes in a network-based model of their collaborations, with a total of 105 840 edges representing over 200 000 collaborations between these researchers [3].

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Initially, networks were constructed based on internal collaborations only (i.e., external authors were not considered). These connected a majority of the nodes into a giant component (GC), but many nodes, representing researchers with all collaborations outside the university, floated unconnected to the GC, obscuring their collaborativeness. In order to keep this extended network manageable, external collaborations from the same university were consolidated into a single node. As a result, this improved the connectedness of the networks. The improvement to connectedness was found to generalize for many other U.S. universities when applying the same network construction techniques to their respective research community data. Due to the high likelihood that two external collaborators at the same university were connected, our confidence in representing them as a single “university node” was thereby reinforced.

Each network edge was assigned a weight proportional to the number of times a collaboration occurred. This was not a straightforward exercise due to the chimeric cataloging of a single researcher’s work: roughly 10% of researchers have multiple Dimensions IDs, often with slight differences such as initializations (e.g., Jane Jack Doe as J. Doe or J.J. Doe). Consolidating these into single nodes is nontrivial, as there are often multiple researchers with similar names, or a single researcher with many aliases, thus requiring very time consuming and careful hand curation. Instead, our approach has been to maintain these discrepancies through to the comparisons between the two cohorts, incurring similar error.

Following this workflow, we identified researchers at the university we could identify as RSE’s. To begin, we searched people with titles such as “Research Software Engineer,” “Scientific Software Engineer,” and “Data Scientist.” This produced a fairly small list. We then supplemented it with anyone with the title of “Postdoctoral Scholar,” “Research Scientist,” or “Research Professor,” who also held accounts on the compute cluster. Hence, a substantial RSE-like cohort could be assembled, consisting of non-tenured, post-graduate computational research role-players in the research community. The 281 researchers who composed the RSE cohort were significantly

fewer than the 2032 nodes in the Research Computing cohort.

B. Small World-ness

The term “small-world network” was coined by Watts and Strogatz [4] to categorize complex sparse real-life networks with much higher clustering coefficients but a similar average path length to sparse random graphs. In prior work, research collaboration networks (RCN) have previously been analyzed and characterized as small-world. One property of these networks is that the elimination of a node in the RCN at random, such as a researcher leaving the university, is unlikely to result in significant reduction in total collaborative research activities. However, key nodes can be identified in these networks with high “hub-like” or “bridge” roles, serving as connections between densely networked subclusters of researcher nodes. For the ASU network, the ratio of clustering coefficients was two orders of magnitude higher than for the random network (~ 510) with a mean path length ratio of 1.35, confirming the small-world structure.

A rendering of the ASU research network is shown in Fig. 1, which visually conveys small-worldness through the density in the middle tiers. While RSE nodes were colored yellow, they are difficult to discern, both because they represent less than 2% of the nodes and because node radii are scaled by degree, betweenness, closeness, and eigenvector centrality measures.

III. NETWORK MEASUREMENT

Table I compares two network measures between the RSE and non-RSE researchers: degree, which suggests collaborativeness, and betweenness centrality, which suggests the extent the researcher plays as a hub-like node. The Mann-Whitney assessment shows that RSEs tend to have more connections or interactions with other nodes compared to the non-RSE group. Interestingly, the RSEs have statistically lower betweenness centrality than their non-RSE counterparts. In other words, the test suggests that RSEs play important roles forming collaborations within their smaller, presumably department or domain-specific, subnetworks, but non-RSEs predominate as critical interdisciplinary bridges or mediators between subnetworks.

TABLE I

COMPARISON OF DEGREE AND BETWEENNESS CENTRALITY MEASURES BETWEEN RSE AND NON-RSE COHORTS.

Mean statistic	RSE nodes	Non-RSE nodes	<i>p</i> -value
Degree	15.63	11.09	<0.001
Betweenness centrality	8.1×10^{-5}	9.6×10^{-5}	<0.001

IV. CONCLUSION

Quantitative analysis, such as presented in this work employing network metrics, can assist in the planning and

Fig. 1. Hierarchical rendering of research collaboration network. RSE nodes are colored yellow. External collaborators have been consolidated into their home institutions and colored blue.

assessment of policies in a research community. In the preceding investigation, a dispersed collection of RSE’s across the university revealed a statistically lower hub-like character despite statistically higher degree. Centralized support for computing cyberinfrastructure corresponded with both higher degree and betweenness centrality for those researchers with cluster accounts, suggesting greater overall and interdisciplinary collaboration. It follows that a policy such as sustained support for a centralized RSE network could augment the RSE connections between subnetworks, thereby improving the interdisciplinary collaborativeness of this cohort and impacting the overall university research community.

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REFERENCES

- [1] D. D. Shah, R. Belshe, K. Kuznia, G. Speyer, and J. Yalim, “Employing a research community network to assess centralized computing impact,” in *Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing*, ser. PEARC ’23. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2023, (in press).
- [2] D. Science, 2018-, accessed 2021-, under license agreement. [Online]. Available: <https://app.dimensions.ai/>
- [3] I. Hossain, S. Kobourov, and N. Merchant, “Institutional knowledge map (kmap),” 2021-, accessed 2022-. [Online]. Available: <https://kmap.arizona.edu>

- [4] D. J. Watts and S. H. Strogatz, “Collective dynamics of ‘small-world’ networks,” *Nature*, vol. 393, no. 6684, pp. 440–442, 1998.
- [5] D. M. Jennewein, J. Lee, C. Kurtz, W. Dizon, I. Shaeffer, A. Chapman, A. Chiquete, J. Burks, A. Carlson, N. Mason, A. Kobwala, T. Jagadeesan, P. Barghav, T. Battelle, R. Belshe, D. McCaffrey, M. Brazil, C. Inumella, K. Kuznia, J. Buzinski, S. Dudley, D. Shah, G. Speyer, and J. Yalim, “The sol supercomputer at arizona state university,” in *Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing*, ser. PEARC '23. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2023.